

Awareness of Global Warming and E-waste Among School Teachers

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Abstract

Global warming means average increase in the earth's temperature and is considered as a major health issue of the 21st century and E-waste is the issue of electronic garbage it's also harm of living animals. To find out the awareness and knowledge about global warming among the school teachers. To find out the awareness and knowledge about E-waste among the school teachers. Self-administered questionnaire was used to collect information from 500 randomly selected school teachers of three different medium. Statistical analyses were performed with the percentage of each question Ethical clearance, informed consent and assent were obtained. Problem to be the major health issue due to global warming. Less than half (45.75%) participants ranked pollution to be the major cause for global warming. Majority of the teachers (57.5%) were willing to walk or cycle instead of driving and only (12%) teachers were willing to plant trees for combating global warming. school teachers exhibited significant difference in respect of their awareness and knowledge towards global warming. Teachers' problem to be the major health. issue due to e-waste. Less than half (52.25%) participants ranked waste electronic materials to be the major cause for e-waste. Majority of the teachers (67%) were willing to reuse of electronic tools and only (14%) teachers were willing to destroy electronic materials. school teachers exhibited significant difference in respect of their awareness and knowledge towards e-waste. Periodic health education regarding global warming and e-waste is still needed to increase awareness and knowledge among the school teachers.

Keywords: *Global Warming, E-waste, Awareness, Green House gases, electronic materials, Knowledge, School teachers.*

Introduction

Global warming means average increase in the earth's temperature and is considered as a major health issue of the 21st century and E-waste is the issue of electronic garbage it's also harm of living animals' Modern society has been growing concern about global environmental issues. The developing countries are experiencing complex, serious and fast-growing pollution problems of their own. Environmental pollution is more than just a health issue; it is a wider social issue Pollution has the potential to destroy homes and communities. Pollution problems are also closely tied to the mode of development in developing countries Despite this, many developing countries either have not developed environmental pollution control measures or have not provided adequate implementation structures to ensure that policies are effective it's also one of the major problems of e-waste that has become an immediate and long term concern as its unregulated accumulation and recycling can lead to major environmental problems such as in air, water, soil and also including physical, chemistry, biology, geology, meteorology, oceanography sociology and human health

In this study, the awareness of electronic waste and global warming are discussed among teachers

Need for the research: -

All living and non-living things. Lives in the atmosphere and chooses air, land and water Uses resources to meet needs. The pressure that comes on the earth. This exceeds the conductivity of the environment, which can lead to serious environmental degradation The water level in the water is getting higher than the water level, you may think so Can lose. From the very beginning, of the environment has been called 'Awakening' It needs to be created and potential dangers to all species of living beings.

Understand the underlying causes and consequences

1. To study and find out the problems of population, health etc.

The way to solve the problem.

2. Considering the need for sustainable use of natural resources.

3. To develop appreciation of caste and habitat management techniques

4. Understanding the feelings of human beings.

Objectives

- 1] To find out the level of awareness of e-waste among school teachers.
- 2) To find out the level of awareness of global warming among school teachers.
- 3] Suggestions for the proper implementation of government rule for environmental issues

Hypothesis

1. Awareness of global warming among school teachers
2. Awareness of E-waste pollution among school teachers
3. Awareness of environmental pollution among school teachers

Methodology

Since the present research is related to the present time, the survey method will be used.

population and sample of the study

The population for the present study consists of all school teachers of Aurangabad District. 500 teachers from 30 schools, Aurangabad District were selected through Random sampling Technique for the study. The overall response Rate was 82%

Tools Used for the Study

For the presented research, the Author has chosen the survey method as the problem is related to the present time. Questionnaires and document will be used among the various tools for the data collection for the survey method. to collect information, school teachers from Aurangabad district were considered. The questionnaires will be filled by the teachers to get the information. Also, the information about the school teachers who have aware about the pollution and percentages will be used to analyze the information obtained and conclusions will be drawn based on it.

Data Analysis

Percentage, Mean, Standard Deviation and t test. This statistical dimension will be

used to analysis the information in present research

Findings:

It is inferred from the above table that 30 %of male school teachers have low 55% of them have average and 87.5% of them have high level of awareness in knowledge. With respect to female teachers 9.2 % of them have low, 23.2% of them have average and 326 % of them have high level of awareness in knowledge. It is inferred from the above table that 37.5% of male school teachers have low, 80.0% of them have average and 47.5% of them have high level of awareness in causes. With respect to female

teachers 14.8%of them have low, 30.5% of them have average and 16.7% of them have high level of awareness in causes. It is inferred from the above table that 27.8% of male school teachers have low, 68.4% of them have average and 60.9% of them have high level of awareness in effects. With respect to female teachers 10.5% of them have low, 28.5 % of them have average and 14.9% of them have high level of awareness in effects. It is inferred from the above table that 57.7% of male school teachers have low, 62.5% of them have average and 20.8% of them have high level of awareness in global problem. With respect to female teachers 7.1% of them have low, 21.1% of them have average and 7.8% of them have high level of awareness in global problem.

Table no 1

level of awareness in global warming and its dimensions of male and female school teachers

global warming and its dimensions	Gender	low		Average		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Knowledge	Male	12	30%	22	55%	35	87.5%
	Female	9	9%	23	23%	32	32%
Cause	Male	15	37.5%	32	80%	19	47.5%
	Female	14	14%	30	30%	16	16%
Effect	Male	11	27.5%	25	62.5%	24	60%
	Female	10	10%	28	28%	14	14%
Global problem	Male	7	57.1%	25	62.5%	8	20%
	Female	7	7%	21	21%	7	7%

Global warming and its dimensions	Male N=400		Female N=100		Calculated value of t test	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Knowledge	45.14	4.87	64.5	6.10	0.86	NS
Cause	66.21	6.40	53.33	5.25	1.48	NS
Effect	60.5	5.80	44	4.80	0.25	NS
Global problem	40.32	3.82	42.66	4.20	1.00	NS

Difference between Male and female school teachers in their Awareness of Global warming and its dimensions

[At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.96]

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated value of ‘t’ (0.86, 1.48, 0.25, and 1.00)

is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.96) at 5% level of Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the male and female school teachers do not differ significantly in their awareness of global warming and its dime

Table no 2

level of awareness in E-waste and its dimensions of male and female school teachers

E-waste and its dimensions	Gender	low		Average		High	
		N	%	N	%	N	%
Knowledge	Male	10	31%	23	52%	32	77.5%
	Female	9	9%	25	21%	22	42%
Cause	Male	18	36.5%	33	78%	9	37.5%
	Female	14	14%	32	30%	26	16%
Effect	Male	10	28.5%	28	50.5%	14	50%
	Female	11	10%	28	28%	14	14%
Global problem	Male	7	57.1%	22	42.5%	8	10%
	Female	8	7%	21	21%	7	7%

It is inferred from the above table that 31 %of male school teachers have low, 52% of them have average and 57.5% of them have high level

of awareness in knowledge. With respect to female teachers 9.2 % of them have low, 25.2% of them have average and 226 % of them have

high level of awareness in knowledge. It is inferred from the above table that 36.5% of male school teachers have low, 78.0% of them have average and 37.5% of them have high level of awareness in causes. With respect to female teachers 14.8% of them have low, 32.5% of them have average and 28.7% of them have high level of awareness in causes. It is inferred from the above table that 28.8% of male school teachers have low, 50.4% of them have average and 50.9% of them have high level of awareness in

effects. With respect to female teachers 28.5% of them have low, 14.5 % of them have average and 57.9% of them have high level of awareness in effects. It is inferred from the above table that 42.7% of male school teachers have low, 10.5% of them have average and 20.8% of them have high level of awareness in global problem. With respect to female teachers 7.1% of them have low, 21.1% of them have average and 7.8% of them have high level of awareness in global problem.

Difference between Male and female school teachers in their Awareness of E-waste and its dimensions

E-Waste and its dimensions	Male N=400		Female N=100		Calculated value of t test	Remarks at 5% level
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Knowledge	40.44	3.42	62.25	5.10	0.86	NS
Cause	62.55	5.40	52.25	4.25	1.45	NS
Effect	30.52	4.80	42.23	3.80	0.20	NS
Global problem	38.25	4.61	40.12	5.20	1.00	NS

[At 5% level of significance, the table value is 1.96

differ significantly in their awareness of E-waste and its dimensions

It is inferred from the above table that the calculated value of ‘t’ (0.86, 1.45, 0.20 and 1.00) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.96) at 5% level of Hence the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, the male and female school teachers do not

Discussion:

The Author selected the study of environmental awareness in the context of global

warming and electronic waste among school teachers in the district of Aurangabad. The problem was thoroughly studied and objectives were set. Collected information through Aadhaar content collection tools related to the problem presented. The information obtained with the help of this statistical technique was analyzed and interpreted. Statistical tables were used to study the environmental awareness of global teachers in the context of global warming and electronic waste among the school teachers in the district of Aurangabad and drew conclusions based on that.

Awareness of the teachers through the questionnaire for the teachers regarding the research problem and hence the breadth of the research problem was noticed and thus the need and usefulness of the presented problem was realized.

Recommendations

- 1] School administrators should arrange short term training programs for teachers, students and society for global warming and electronic waste awareness.
- 2] At the primary and secondary level, the issue of environment should be kept as a separate unit. Therefore, this subject should be included in the syllabus offered by the State of Maharashtra.

3] There is a need to create e-waste awareness program to educate the society on how to manage e-waste

4] Scientists, NGOs, government representatives and corporate bodies. The e-waste disposal system proposed by them can help projects that are successfully implemented

Conclusion

In the present case the Author has summarized the research. And the important part of this case is that the findings obtained by analyzing and interpreting the information from above given. According to that conclusion, the hypothesis has been examined and based on the findings, some difficulties have been noticed and some recommendations have been suggested accordingly. Also, the teacher questionnaire and list used for research in the reference section

Reference bibliography

Books

- 1] **Bhandarkar, K.M. [2007]** Environmental Education. [Second Edition]. Pune Nityanutan Prakashan.
- 2] **Dutt, B.S.V. [1998]** Environmental Education, The Need of the hour
- 3] **Patanakar, P.S., [2000]** - Teaching, learning strategies in Environmental Education

- 4] **Singh, Bhopal [1991]**, Environmental Education and Environmental Protection,
- 5] **Bhintade, Vs. Ra. [1994]**, Educational Research Methods, New Publications, Pune
- 6] **b. Govt. Bapat. [1486]** Research methods and tools
- 7] **Grades 8, 9 and 10: Our environment**, environment and sustainable development, Textbook State Board of Secondary and Higher Secondary Education, Pune-04 Maharashtra
- 8] **Pandit, Bansi, Bihari [1997]** Numerical and Qualitative Research in Education Pune: Nityanutan Prakashan.
- 9] **Pawar, N.G. [2007]** Modern Thought Flow in Indian Education, Pune: Nityanutan Prakashan.
- 10] **Due to, Rs. And Umathe, V.T. [1987]** Fundamentals of Academic Research [Version]. Nagpur: Maharashtra University Granth Nirmiti Mandal.
- 11] **Bapat B.G. [1986]** Educational Research, New Publications Pune.
- 12] **Global warming short story [2004]:** Mark Maslin
- 13] **Digital rubbish a natural history of electronics [2011]:** Jennifer Gabrys

Monthly

- 1] **Chaudhary, K. R [January 2007] Mumbai:** Evergreen Publications.
- 2] **Monroe, M.C. and Kalpan, S. [1988]** Environment problem solving in the classroom
- 3] **R. W. and Mayer, V. J. (1991)** The impact of TV program on the public environment Knowledge
- 4] **Chavan Kishor, Sampa, 2011** ShikshanTarang [Monthly] Nashik: Inlight Publication.

web sites

- www.google.com
www.doscovery.com
www.environmentalpollution.com
www.animalplanet.com
www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2007/10/071022094516.ht
www.youtube.com